

RTBV and RTSV incidence on TKM6 and TN1 at different days after transplanting. IRRRI, 1987 WS.

indexed by ELISA for the presence of RTBV and RTSV.

In 1987, at 92 DT (when TN1 had 100% infection with both RTBV and RTSV), TKM6 had 69% infection with RTBV only (see figure). In the 1988 trial, when tungro incidence was relatively lower, RTBV incidence on

IR20 was 0.6% at 14 DT and increased to 2.6% at 55 DT. Very low infection with both RTBV and RTSV and no infection with RTSV alone were recorded.

Infectivity test of green leafhopper (GLH) collected at 44 DT from IR20 plots yielded a low percentage of

Infectivity on TN1 seedlings of GLH collected 44 DT from field plots planted to IR20 and TN1. IRRRI, 1988 WS.

Source of GLH	GLH tested (no.)	GLH transmitted (%)		
		RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
IR20	129	0.01	0.01	0
TN1	132	42	13	2

infective leafhoppers; GLH collected from an adjacent field planted to TN1 with 30% tungro incidence had high infectivity (see table).

Because transmission of RTBV by GLH depends on the presence of RTSV, RTBV incidence will not increase remarkably nor become RTBV + RTSV if the population of RTSV-infected or RTBV + RTSV-infected plants is very low. □

Bacterial blight (BB) resistance in some Nepal rice cultivars

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We evaluated nine traditional and two improved rices reported resistant to BB in Nepal in the greenhouse at IRRRI

against Philippine races of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*. Plants were clip-inoculated at maximum tillering with inoculum (10^8 CFU/ml) from each race group. Lesion development was measured on 10 randomly inoculated leaves of each cultivar 14 d after inoculation.

Reaction to the races varied significantly among cultivars (see table).

Rato anadi was highly resistant to races 2 and 5, Saeto anadi was resistant only to race 5. Laxmi was moderately resistant to races 1, 4, and 5. In general, the Nepalese rices had low levels of resistance to the Philippine races of *X. c* pv. *oryzae*. □

Reaction of some Nepalese rice cultivars to 6 Philippine races of *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae*. IRRRI, 1989.

Cultivar	Lesion length ^a (cm)						Mean
	1 (PXO61)	2 (PXO86)	3 (PXO79)	4 (PXO71)	5 (PXO112)	6 (PXO99)	
Ghaiya	5.14 c	10.40 bc	7.21 c	19.41 b	6.42 c	35.65 a	14.04 bc
Saeto anadi	27.48 a	26.54 ab	16.70 b	23.57 ab	1.35 c	25.21 ab	20.14 a
Rato anadi	18.06 bc	1.24 d	12.61 c	23.03 ab	1.08 d	28.87 a	14.15 bc
Choto marshi	21.89 a-c	11.87 c	12.91 bc	22.93 ab	17.56 bc	30.15 a	19.55 a
Ramdulari	18.68 b	20.88 ab	12.99 b	18.90 b	14.11 b	30.45 a	19.34 a
Malbhog	12.27 b	9.04 b	8.89 b	10.79 b	12.70 b	28.68 a	13.73 bc
Gadar	12.69 bc	22.42 a	8.74 c	8.48 c	21.67 b	32.93 a	17.82 ab
Sataraj	14.63 ab	11.67 ab	7.40 b	18.17 a	14.77 ab	18.55 a	14.20 bc
Jaswa	16.31 bc	25.18 ab	16.51 bc	13.67 c	13.25 c	28.95 a	18.98 a
Janaki ^b	10.07 b	20.72 a	8.66 b	8.76 b	5.53 b	11.84 ab	10.93 c
Laxmi ^b	4.86 b	18.13 a	9.94 ab	6.62 b	4.10 b	17.62 a	10.21 c
TN1	22.56 b	21.24 b	17.02 b	23.91 ab	7.04 c	32.89 a	20.78 a
Mean	15.39 bc	16.61 b	11.63 cd	16.52 b	9.96 d	26.81 a	16.15

^aDisease was assessed by lesion length: 0.0-3.0 cm = resistant, 3.1-7 cm = moderately resistant, 7.1-10.0 cm = moderately susceptible, 10.1 cm or longer = susceptible. In a row, means having a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bImproved cultivar.

Insect resistance

Screening rice varieties for damage caused by *Oebalus insularis* (Stål)

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In 1985, insect pests and diseases affected about 50% of the rice area in Cuba. The pests that caused the greatest damage were water weevil and stink bug. *O. insularis* is the most plentiful and widespread bug species. Use of resistant varieties plays an important role in widely accepted integrated control.

During spring 1987, we evaluated commercial varieties IR880, J104, Amistad 82, and Blue Belle for *O. insularis* incidence. (Blue Belle is tolerant of rice stink bug *Oebalus pugnax* in the U.S.)

Five 1-m² plots were sown per variety. The agronomic practices were common to all treatments. Complete insect control was used from seeding to the milk stage. In the milk stage, varieties were infested at two levels, 0 (check) and 0.3 insect/panicle in 0.16-m² cages. Population levels were determined at 3-d intervals and additional releases were made to maintain the insect levels to 12 d after infestation. When the milk stage ended, insects were eliminated with insecticide.

Table 1 shows the results from evaluating stylet sheath identified with acid fuschin solution on randomly selected panicles. IR880 showed the highest insect incidence and Blue Belle the lowest. There was no significant difference in average punctures/panicle and average punctures/grain.

We found a trend in number of stylet sheath, in ascending order from Blue Belle, Amistad 82, J104, and IR880: apparently a certain tolerance exists.

We also compared yields in cages with and without insects (Table 2). Percentage of infestation did not differ significantly between varieties. □

Table 1. Feeding rate of *Oebalus insularis* (Stal) on 4 rice varieties. Havana, Cuba, 1985.

Variety	Stylet sheaths	
	no./panicle	no./grain
J104	27.98	0.30
Amistad 82	28.28	0.31
IR880	40.84	0.44
Blue Belle	24.14	0.29

Table 2. Effect on rice yield of four varieties of damage caused by *Oebalus insularis*.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)		Infestation (%)
	0 insect /panicle (check)	0.3 insect/panicle	
J104	6.5	5.2	20.4
Amistad 82	7.4	5.9	20.1
IR880	5.1	3.9	24.2
Blue Belle	5.6	4.7	16.0

Reactions of gall midge (GM)-resistant rice accessions to yellow stem borer (YSB), leafroller (LF), and rice blast (BI)

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We evaluated 794 rice accessions for resistance to GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) in two field trials and identified 205 new sources of resistance. Of these, 24 were tested against YSB

Scirpophaga incertulas (Walker), LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée), and leaf BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. CO 37 and IR50 were the susceptible checks.

Almost all GM-resistant accessions were either resistant or moderately resistant to YSB. IET9576 exhibited high resistance (see table). IET10251 and ARC10847 were resistant to LF. RP2238-112-38-57 was free of BI and RP160741-3, RP2311-225-229, IET10251, RP2362-16-5-1, RP2432-102-11-6, and IET9552 were resistant (see table). Only IET10251 was resistant to both insects and BI. □

Reaction^a of GM-resistant rice accessions to YSB, LF, and BI. Madurai, India.

Accession	YSB		LF		Blast damage rating
	Deadheart (%)	Damage score	Leaf damage (%)	Damage score	
RP1607-401-3	9.1	1	45.2	7	1
RP2199-16-2-2-1	2.8	1	30.3	5	5
RP2199-102-14-19-10	8.0	1	49.6	7	5
RP2235-136-65-10	3.5	1	69.9	9	6
RP2238-62-38-72	7.1	1	70.5	9	5
RP2238-112-38-57	8.4	1	47.7	7	0
RP2311-225-229	8.5	1	44.9	7	1
RP2311-35748	12.8	1	77.0	9	3
RP2362-16-5-1	12.2	1	79.6	9	2
RP2432-102-11-6	11.3	1	67.5	9	2
RP2432-111-1-3	8.3	1	48.6	7	3
IET9552	6.7	1	71.5	9	2
IET9576	0.0	0	54.4	9	5
IET9698	5.3	1	62.7	9	5
IET10251	4.7	1	8.3	1	1
Nagrasal	9.0	1	12.9	3	3
W1263	3.8	1	17.7	3	4
ARC595 1	2.3	1	26.3	5	5
Phalguna	12.5	1	71.9	9	5
ARC10847	13.6	1	9.2	1	4
S2204	11.1	1	30.7	5	3
ARC5823	18.6	1	36.7	7	4
Balam	10.2	1	19.4	3	3
Banglei	13.7	1	13.4	3	3
CO 37	21.3	3	80.0	9	4
IR50	22.2	3	77.0	9	9

^aStandard evaluation system for rice.

Difference of resistance to rice stem borer (SB) in indica and japonica rices

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We evaluated 47 commercial rice varieties (9 conventional indica varieties, 25 conventional japonica varieties, 7 hybrid indica varieties, and 6 hybrid japonica varieties) for resistance to rice SB *Chilo suppressalis* Walker in 1986 and 1987. IR40 and Shanyou 63 were the resistant and susceptible checks.